

The Influence Of The Quality Of Population Documents Service Through 3 In 1 Program To People Satisfaction In The Department Of Population And Civil Registration In North Halmahera District

Oktovianus Panusi¹, Muhlis Hafel², Milwan³, Anfas⁴

¹ Students in the Master of Public Administration Study Program, Universitas Terbuka, Indonesia

^{2,3} Faculty of Law, Social Sciences and Political Sciences, Universitas Terbuka, Indonesia

⁴ Faculty of Economi, Universitas Terbuka, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This study aims to examine the effect of the independent variable, namely the quality of service in 3 in 1 program population documents measured from theory according to Zeithaml, V.A.A. Parasuraman and L.L Berry, (1990) through Tangible, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Emphaty dimensions to the dependent variable, namely community satisfaction in North Halmahera Regency. This research uses a quantitative approach, using primary data through questionnaires. Respondents in this study were people in North Halmahera Regency as users of the 3 in 1 program population document service. The population used was 117,272 people, the sample used was 99 respondents. Data were analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis (Multiple linear regression) and data testing was performed with the assistance of SPSS version 24. Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis showed that partially the quality of service in 3 in 1 population residence documents affected community satisfaction in North Halmahera Regency. Simultaneous testing results on Tangible dimensions, Reliability, Responsiveness, and Assurance, have a significant effect on community satisfaction while Emphaty has a negative relationship on community satisfaction. The value of the coefficient of determination shows that the quality of service in 3 in 1 program population documents measured from Tangible, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, and Emphaty dimensions is 73.3% while the remaining 26.7% is influenced by other factors of this research model.

KEYWORDS : Service Quality, Tangible, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Emphaty, Community Satisfaction

I. INTRODUCTION

The state is obliged to serve every citizen or resident to fulfill their basic rights and needs within the framework of public services. Public service according to Law Number 25 of 2009, is an activity or a series of activities in the framework of fulfilling the basic rights of service in accordance with statutory regulations for every citizen and resident for administrative goods, services and / or services provided by Service Providers. Public.

In this regard, the government has also updated Law Number 32 of 2004 with Law Number 23 of 2014 concerning Regional Government, which is one way of bringing government closer to the community. The

implementation of policies through Law Number 23 of 2014, has brought new implications for the government system in the regions, because both the provincial and district / city governments have the authority and obligation to form and run their own wheels of government in accordance with the applicable laws for the purpose welfare of the people, so as a consequence of the implementation of this law, the public services received by the public or the public must be better than the previous era.

The government's efforts through Law Number 23 Year 2006 as amended by Law Number 24 Year 2013 concerning Population Administration Article 69 Paragraph 1, namely; The implementing agency or authorized official, according to their responsibilities, is obliged to issue a resident registration document. Therefore, the Regional Government of North Halmahera Regency in providing population document services to the community through one of its policies is that if someone manages a population document, then that day it is taken care of, that day will be finished. This policy is based on the consideration of a control range with a fairly long distance and geographic location of North Halmahera Regency with a total area of 22,507.32 Km² covering a land area of 4,951.61 Km² (22%) and a sea of 17,555.71 Km² (78 %).

As for the population document service location, currently it is still focused on the Department of Population and Civil Registration in North Halmahera Regency. Therefore, if a resident is going to take care of one of the population documents, then the resident will pay a large amount of money, such as; transportation costs, food costs, lodging costs and other costs, because the distance between a village to the sub-district capital is quite far, especially with the population document service location which is located in the district city. One evidence of public complaints in the processing of a population document, which seems still very convoluted or complicated, as posted on the social media "Facebook" on July 2, 2019, said by a community member from Ruko village, Tobelo Utara District on behalf of Runo Kusame stated that:

" the requirements for changing the Family Card are very complicated eee.., even the officer cannot explain the rules well, poor eee.. is at counter 3"

This statement proves that the Department of Population and Civil Registration of North Halmahera Regency is considered not optimal in carrying out its service duties to meet the interests and needs of the community. Along with the efforts of the North Halmahera regency government to continue to improve the quality of services to the community, then based on Government Regulation Number 38 of 2017 concerning Regional Innovation, which is further implemented by the North Halmahera Regency Population and Civil Registration Service, is implemented by creating and implementing an innovative service program. To be able to optimize population document services for the community, namely through the 3 in 1 program. This program intends for every resident who comes to make a population document, once the resident submits a request for publication of population documents, he will get 3 population documents at once, even more. For example; if residents make a marriage registration request, the officer will record and issue 3 (three) population documents at once or even more, among others; 2 (two) Sheet of Marriage Certificate, 1 (one) Sheet of Family Card for newly married couples and 2 (two) pieces of KTP-El status change from unmarried to married for newly married couples.

Efforts to improve the quality of services carried out by the population and civil registration services of North Halmahera regency, can be proven by the increasing number of population document ownership since the last 3 years, 2016 to the end of 2018, as in table 1.

Table 1
 Population Document Ownership Data

Population Documents	2016	2018	Increase in Number of Ownership	Percentage of Increase	Ket
Birth certificate	150.201	187.387	37.186	25%	
Death certificate	3.289	4.634	1.345	41%	
Marriage certificate	22.829	25.587	2.758	12%	
Divorce Certificate	135	220	85	63%	
Family card	48.278	51.259	2.981	6%	
Electronic Identity Card	106.148	117.272	11.124	10%	

Data: Department of Population and Civil Registration 2019 (processed results 2019)

In addition to an increase in population document ownership, according to the North Halmahera Regency Population and Civil Registration Office (2019), it has conducted a survey on the index of community satisfaction with service quality through 9 assessment elements, including: Requirements, Procedures, Service Time, Fees / Rates, Service Products, Implementer competence, implementer behavior, facilities and infrastructure, handling complaints, then the calculation result is: 83.250 with the interpretation that the quality of service is good (satisfied) and service performance is good (satisfied).

Given that community satisfaction is a very important element of public service value because it is related to the performance of the local government of North Halmahera Regency to the community, researchers are interested in conducting further research to examine the effect of community satisfaction on the 3 in 1 population document service program through five dimensions of analysis, namely Tangible (physical evidence), Reliability dimension, Responsiveness dimension, Assurance dimension, Empathy dimension (empathy), Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Berry, (1990).

Based on the background of the problems mentioned above, the title of this research is "The Effect of Service Quality of Population Documents 3 In 1 Program on Community Satisfaction at the Department of Population and Civil Registration in North Halmahera Regency".

Population administration services

According to Pasolong (2011: 3), Administration is a series of activities carried out by a group of people in collaboration to achieve goals on the basis of being effective, efficient and rational. According to Musanef (1996: 1), Administration is the activity of a group of people through regular stages and is led effectively and efficiently, using the means needed to achieve the desired goals. According to Handyaningrat and Soewarno (1996: 2), administration is an activity which includes taking notes, correspondence, light bookkeeping, typing, agendas and so on which are technical in administration.

In the mandate of Law Number 24 of 2013 concerning Population Administration, every resident has rights and obligations, the obligation of each resident is to comply with all the regulations that have been stipulated in these laws and regulations, the documents of which are issued by the Population and Civil Registration Service in all Regencies / cities in Indonesia, while the right of every resident is to be protected and treated fairly in fulfilling all population affairs that have been determined by the government based on applicable law.

Public Service

Public service according to Government Regulation Number 96 of 2012 concerning Implementation of Law Number 25 of 2009 concerning Public Services, is an activity or series of activities in order to fulfill service needs in accordance with statutory regulations for every citizen and resident of goods, services and services. / or administrative services provided by Public Service Providers. In the Decree of the Minister of State Apparatus Empowerment Number 63 of 2003 General Guidelines for the Implementation of Public Services are all service activities carried out by public service providers as an effort to meet the needs of service recipients as well as to implement the provisions of laws and regulation.

According to Moenir (2015: 26) that public service is an activity carried out by a person or group of people based on factors through certain systems, procedures and methods in order to fulfill the interests of others according to their rights. Meanwhile, according to Sinambela (2014: 5), public service is the fulfillment of wants and needs carried out by the government or state administrators for people who have every activity, whether profitable or not in a group or unit, and offer satisfaction even though the results are not tied to a product physically.

Service Quality

According to Lewis & Booms (1983: 99), Service quality is a measure of how well the service level delivered matches customer expectations. " This definition emphasizes the measure of how well the level of service provided is in accordance with customer expectations. Service quality according to Zeithaml, Parasuraman, and Berry (1990: 19), Service quality is the extent of discrepancy between customers expectations or desires and their perceptions, which means that service quality is a gap / mismatch between consumer expectations or desires and consumer perceptions.

According to Tjiptono (2014: 268) the definition of service quality focuses on efforts to meet the needs and desires of consumers and the accuracy of their delivery to balance consumer expectations. According to Tjiptono (2016: 59) states that "Service quality is the level of excellence expected and control over that level of excellence is to meet customer desires".

Service Quality Dimensions

According to Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Berry, (1990: 19) there are five main dimensions that determine service quality consisting of: 1. reliability, 2. responsiveness, 3. assurance (which includes competence, courtesy, credibility, and security), 4. empathy (which includes access, communication and understanding the customer), and 5. tangible.

Satisfaction Level

According to Tjiptono (2015: 146) customer satisfaction is "a feeling of pleasure or disappointment in someone who comes after comparing perceptions of the performance (results) of a product with expectations". According to Kotler & Keller (2016: 150) states that:

"Satisfaction is a person's feelings of pleasure or dissatisfaction that result from comparing a product's perceived performance or outcome to expectations. If the performance falls short of 37 expectations, the outcome is dissatisfied. If it matches expectations, the customer is satisfied or delighted". Which means satisfaction is a feeling of satisfaction or disappointment for someone resulting from a comparison of product performance or results with expectations.

Therefore, customer satisfaction or feelings of satisfaction are largely determined by the service provider. According to Barata (2003: 11), service providers are parties who can provide certain services to consumers, either in the form of services in the form of provision or delivery of goods or services.

Relation between Public Service Quality and Community Satisfaction Level

According to Lukman (2000: 8), one measure of the success of providing quality service depends on the level of customer satisfaction served. According to Harbani (2007: 135) Quality service or excellent customer-oriented service is highly dependent on customer satisfaction. Because it is a quality has a very big influence on community satisfaction. According to Tjiptono (2014: 353) satisfaction comes from the Latin "Satis" which means good enough, adequate and "Facio" which means doing or making. Furthermore, according to Tjiptono (2007: 349), satisfaction is simply defined as an effort to fulfill something or make something adequate. From some of the definitions above, it can be concluded that satisfaction is a function of the difference between perceived performance and expectations. According to Tjiptono (2012: 125) by paying attention to the quality of service to consumers, it will increase the consumer quality satisfaction index which is measured in any measure. According to Lupiyoadi (2006: 155), the main determining factor for community satisfaction is the perception of service quality.

Research Framework

The framework of research can be seen in Figure 2.1 the following framework:

Pic 1

Picture 1. Research framework
(Source: Results of the 2019 analysis)

II. RESEARCH METHOD

In this study, researchers used a quantitative method with a descriptive research approach, because there were variables to be examined and the purpose was to present a description of the relationship between the variables studied. All data in this study will use a sample obtained from the population in North Halmahera district.

The population in this study were all the people of North Halmahera Regency (117,272 people) who had population documents scattered in the North Halmahera Regency Government.

From a population of 117,272 people used as subjects in this study, 100 samples were taken from people who already have Civil Registration Deeds, Family Cards and Electronic KTPs in North Halmahera Regency.

The instrument in this study was carried out by distributing questionnaires to respondents. The questionnaire is structured into two parts and will be distributed directly to 115 respondents in North Halmahera district to be filled out. The questionnaire is divided into two parts, the first part regarding the identity of the respondent, and the second part contains a list of statements regarding the effect of service quality as an independent variable or independent variable (X) which consists of Tangible (X1), Reliability (X2), Responsiveness (X3) dimensions. Assurance (X4), and Empathy (X5), and community satisfaction as the dependent variable (Y).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1) The Effect of the Service Quality of the 3 In 1 Population Document Service on the Level of Community Satisfaction as seen from the Tangible Dimension.

The test results show that the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality as measured from the Tangible dimension has a statistically significant effect on community satisfaction in North Halmahera Regency. Thus hypothesis 1 is accepted or supported because it is empirically proven.

According to the results of the frequency testing in this study, the public response to the tangible dimension can be seen the percentage of the response to tangibles in the pie chart image 2 Tangible Percentage.

Picture 2. Pie Chart *Tangible* Persentase
(Source of processed data 2019)

The community response to the Tangible dimension was 36% very satisfied, 45% satisfied and 18% quite satisfied. This means that community satisfaction is supported by service quality seen from the Tangibles dimension. This means that good service quality is able to support increased community satisfaction with the 3 In 1 Program Population Document Service. The higher the Quality of the 3 In 1 Program Population Document Service in the Tangibles dimension, the higher the community's satisfaction with the services of the Population and Civil Registration Service in North Halmahera Regency.

2) The Effect of the Service Quality of the 3 In 1 Population Document Service on the Level of Community Satisfaction as seen from the Reliability Dimension.

The test results show that the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality as measured by the Reliability dimension has a statistically significant effect on community satisfaction in North Halmahera Regency. Thus hypothesis 2 is accepted or supported because it is empirically proven.

According to the results of the frequency testing in this study, the response of the community in North Halmahera Regency to the Reliability dimension can be seen the percentage of the response to Reliability in the pie chart image 3 Reliability Percentage

Picture 3. Pie Chart *Reliability*Presentase
 (Source of processed data 2019)

The community response to the Reliability dimension is 36% very satisfied, 43% satisfied and 20% quite satisfied. This means that community satisfaction with the 3 In 1 Population Document Service is supported by service quality seen from the Reliability dimension. This means that the good 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality is able to support increased community satisfaction in North Halmahera regency. The higher the Service Quality of the 3 In 1 Population Document Service in the Reliability dimension, the higher the community's satisfaction with the services of the Population and Civil Registration Service in North Halmahera.

3) The Effect of Service Quality of Population Documents 3 In 1 Program on Community Satisfaction Level seen from the Responsiveness Dimension.

The test results show that the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality as measured by the Responsiveness dimension has a statistically significant effect on community satisfaction in North Halmahera Regency. Thus hypothesis 3 is accepted or supported because it is empirically proven.

According to the results of the frequency testing in this study, the public response to the Responsiveness dimension can be seen the percentage of the response to Responsiveness in the pie chart image.

Picture 4. Pie Chart *Responseveness* Presentase
 (Source of processed data 2019)

The community response to the Responsiveness dimension was 32% very satisfied, 37% satisfied and 26% quite satisfied. This means that the community's satisfaction with the 3 In 1 Population Document Service is supported by the quality of service seen from the Responsiveness dimension. This means that the good 3 In 1

Population Document Service Quality is able to support the improvement of community satisfaction in North Halmahera. The higher the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality in the Responsiveness dimension, the higher the community's satisfaction with the services of the Population and Civil Registration Service in North Halmahera Regency.

4) The Effect of Service Quality of Population Documents 3 In 1 Program on Community Satisfaction Level seen from the Assurance Dimension.

The test results show that the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality as measured by the Assurance dimension has a statistically significant effect on community satisfaction in North Halmahera Regency. Thus hypothesis 4 is accepted or supported because it is empirically proven.

According to the results of the frequency in this study, the response of the community in North Halmahera regency to the dimension of Assurance can be seen in the percentage of the response to Assurance in the pie chart 5.

Picture 5. Pie Chart Assurance Percentase
(Source of processed data 2019)

The community response to the Assurance dimension is 37% very satisfied, 43% satisfied and 15% quite satisfied. This means that community satisfaction with the 3 In 1 Program Population Document Service is supported by service quality seen from the dimension of Assurance. This means that the good 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality is able to support increased community satisfaction in North Halmahera regency. The higher the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality in the Assurance dimension, the higher the community's satisfaction with the Population and Civil Registration Service in North Halmahera.

5) The Effect of the Service Quality of the 3 In 1 Population Document Service on the Level of Community Satisfaction as seen from the Empathy Dimension.

The test results show that the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality as measured from the Empathy dimension has a statistically significant effect on community satisfaction in North Halmahera Regency. Thus hypothesis 5 is accepted or supported because it is empirically proven.

According to the results of the frequency testing in this study, showing the response of the community in North Halmahera regency to the Empathy dimension can be seen the percentage of responses to Emphaty in the pie chart image6 Emphaty Percentase.

Picture 6. Pie Chart *Empathy Percentase*
(Source of processed data 2019)

The community response to the Empathy dimension was very satisfied, 33%, 43% satisfied and 20% quite satisfied. This means that community satisfaction with the 3 In 1 Population Document Service is supported by the quality of service seen from the Empathy dimension. This means that the good 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality is able to support increased community satisfaction in North Halmahera regency. The higher the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality in the Empathy dimension, the higher the community's satisfaction with the services of the Population and Civil Registration Service in North Halmahera Regency.

6) The Effect of the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality on Community Satisfaction in North Halmahera

The test results showed that the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Quality had a statistically significant effect on community satisfaction. Simultaneous statistical test results (F test) Service Quality of Program Population Documents 3 In one test of the dimensions of Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Empathy on community satisfaction in North Halmahera Regency, the Fcount = 51.107 figure is obtained, this figure is greater than the Ftable value = 2.467 in degrees of freedom (df 1 is k-1 = 4 and df2 is nk = 95). At the p-value level in the significant column is, 000 this figure is less than 0.05. This means that service quality as measured by the dimensions of Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Empathy together, has a significant effect on community satisfaction in North Halmahera Regency.

Based on the F test, it can be stated that the quality of service greatly affects community satisfaction in North Halmahera regency. This can be seen in the coefficient of determination (R²). Correlation (r) shows the R Square number of, 733 or 73.3%. This figure means that 73.3% of the level of community satisfaction in North Halmahera district can be explained by the 3 In 1 Program Population Document Service Quality which is measured from the dimensions of Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Empathy. While the remaining 26.7% is caused by other factors outside of this test.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusions

One of the policies of the North Halmahera Regency Government in optimizing population document services to the community is that if someone manages a population document, then that day it is taken care of, that day will be done. In addition, the Regional Government continues to strive to improve the quality of services to the community, by implementing an innovative and integrated population document service program, namely the 3 in 1 service program with the aim that the community who will take care of population documents, once taking care of it, they will receive 3 population documents at once, so that the public can feel satisfaction with the public services provided by the local government.

In the government's efforts, it turns out that there are still complaints from the public who when processing a population document, it seems that they are still very convoluted or complicated. In fact, according to the results of a survey on the index of community satisfaction with service quality at the Department of Population and Civil Registration in North Halmahera Regency through 9 assessment elements, including: Requirements, Procedures, Service Time, Cost / Tariff, Service Products, Implementer Competence, Implementer Behavior, Facilities and Infrastructure, Complaint Handling, amounting to: 83,250 with the interpretation that the service quality is good (satisfied) and service performance is good (satisfied). If it is explained based on the results of research and discussion, it will be known:

- (1) Tangible statistically has a significant effect on community satisfaction. If Tangibel owned by the Department of Population and Civil Registration in North Halmahera Regency is getting better, the better the quality of service so that the community's satisfaction with the 3 In 1 Program Population Document Service in North Halmahera Regency will be higher.
- (2) Reliability statistically has a significant effect on community satisfaction. If the reliability owned by the Department of Population and Civil Registration in North Halmahera Regency is getting better, the better the quality of service so that the community's satisfaction with the 3 In 1 Program Population Document Service in North Halmahera Regency will be higher.
- (3) Statistically responsiveness has a significant effect on community satisfaction. If the responsiveness carried out by the staff of the Population and Civil Registration Service in North Halmahera Regency is getting better, then the better the quality of service so that the community's satisfaction with the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Program in North Halmahera Regency will be higher.
- (4) Statistically, assurance has a significant effect on community satisfaction. If the assurance carried out by the staff of the Population and Civil Registration Service in North Halmahera Regency is getting better, then the better the quality of service so that the community's satisfaction with the 3 In 1 Population Document Service Program in North Halmahera Regency will be higher.
- (5) Emphaty has an inverse or negative relationship with community satisfaction. This is intended if employees of the Population and Civil Registration Service in North Halmahera Regency in the 3 In 1 Program Population Document Service, lack Emphaty but there is community satisfaction with the 3 In 1 Program Population Document Service carried out by the Population and Civil Registration Service in North Halmahera Regency. .
- (6) Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Emphaty simultaneously have an effect on community satisfaction. The satisfaction of the community in North Halmahera regency with the quality of the population document service of the 3 in 1 program carried out by the Department of Population and Civil Registration in North Halmahera Regency is 73.3%. This means that if Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Emphaty are good, the service quality of the 3 In 1 Program Population Documents is also good, so this has an impact on the satisfaction of the people of North Halmahera regency as well as increasing the service of the 3 In 1 Program Population Documents in North Halmahera Regency.

Suggestions

- (1) The North Halmahera Regency Government Budget policy must pay more attention to the 3 In 1 program population document services that have been implemented because it has been proven that there has been an increase in the percentage (%) of population document ownership since the last 3 years, namely 2016 to the end of 2018, among other things. ; Birth certificates increased by 25%, death certificates increased by 41%, marriage certificates increased by 12%, divorce certificates increased by 63%, family cards increased by 6% and KTP-El increased by 10%, thereby increasing public satisfaction with public services at the Population and Civil Registration Service. North Halmahera Regency.
- (2) Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Emphaty are important factors in improving service quality, so it is suggested to the North Halmahera Regency Population and Civil Registration

Service to improve or add Tangible facilities and employees of the North Halmahera Regency Population and Civil Registration Service need to increase Reliability. , Responsiveness, Assurance and Emphaty in implementing the 3 in 1 population document service.

- (3) It is suggested that further research can add research variables, especially independent variables. Because there are still other factors beyond those that have been studied at 26.7% which can affect community satisfaction.

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